

Liudmyla VOVCHUK*, Wiktor WERNER**

WOMEN'S THEMES ON UKRAINIAN AND POLISH HISTORICAL YOUTUBE CHANNELS

- Abstract -

The article is devoted to the issue of the presence of women as heroes of multimedia products presented on YouTube in Ukrainian and Polish versions. The purpose of the article is to determine the place, role of women, and the context in which they appear in films, based on the analysis of video materials on Ukrainian and Polish history from antiquity to the present day, posted on leading Ukrainian and Polish historical YouTube channels. To find out the top female figures that arouses the greatest interest from viewers. The study combines quantitative methods (descriptive statistics, correspondence analysis) and machine learning algorithms (Decision Tree).

As a result of the study, it was found that today the creators of Ukrainian and Polish historical YouTube channels notice the presence of women in history and do not ignore women's themes. The theme of women is also present in videos concentrated on "men's topics". Only there the woman does not have the main role, but is important or simply mentioned in the role of mother, wife, sister, friend of the male protagonist.

In most cases, creators of videos about women on Ukrainian historical YouTube channels provide not only information about their origin, place of birth, family, status, preferences, but also try to tell about various sometimes piquant, mysterious aspects of their lives. This is explained by the desire of producers to attract the attention of viewers. It is worth noting that the attention of video producers on Ukrainian historical YouTube channels is more focused on producing videos about women in the history of Ukraine, rather than about women in general history. Such a phenomenon is explained by the issue of the revival of

* Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan, Poznan, Poland (luda_vovchuk@ukr.net).

** Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznan, Poznan, Poland (werner@amu.edu.pl).

historical memory and historical consciousness, which are at the heart of the country's development.

Our research, both quantitative (correspondence analysis, statistical analysis) and qualitative (analysis of plot models), shows that YouTube as a Web 2.0 tool has created new and attractive communication models and the functioning of historical narratives, breaking the patterns of traditional literature and even becoming an alternative.

Keywords: women's themes; Ukrainian historical YouTube channels; Polish historical YouTube channels; machine learning algorithms "Decision Tree".

Statement of the problem

For centuries, women's main role was perceived as housekeeping and motherhood. However, since the end of the 19th century, this stereotypical idea began to change and women increasingly began to take active positions in society. Today, women occupy key positions in various fields, from politics to science and art. In this way, they demonstrate their importance, influence, professionalism and equality with men. But the idea has been formed that the leading role in shaping the country's history belongs to men. And this applies both to its traditional coverage through the prism of writing books and scientific articles, and through its presentation on social networks. Among these, YouTube is the most influential and convenient platform not only in Ukraine and Poland, but also in the world as a whole.

Polish researchers conducted an interesting study in 2023 on the place and role of women on popular Polish historical YouTube channels¹. The main research question was whether women are marginalized in the narratives contained in the sources under discussion, in what context they appear, and how the films in which they appear are perceived. In addition, the authors considered the form of historical narratives.

¹ W. Werner, N. Sypniewska, Z.Szymczak, M. Stachura, A.Strykowski, B. Staszak, A. Trzoss, C. Kleist, *Women in the digital streams of history. Women's themes on Polish YouTube history channels*, "Historyka Studia Metodologiczne", 2023, pp. 409-435.

The study was conducted in several stages. The researchers selected the 5 most popular Polish historical YouTube channels and analysed 551 films that were made between 2013 and 2021.

Then, it was annotated using seven groups of tags corresponding to the content of the sources – regarding the functioning of female characters and the themes of the films. As a result of the analysis, it was observed that the thesis about the absolute dominance of male characters in historical narratives does not fully correspond to reality in the conditions of Web 2.0 sources in quantitative terms, while in content terms – it cannot be accepted unconditionally in the context of the very diverse use of female themes in social networks.

In addition, the authors found that the largest and most influential historical channel on Polish YouTube in terms of the reach of the films it presents is “Historia bez cenzury” (“History uncensored, History without censorship”). In the films presented on this channel, women are most often presented in a comedic and satirical style. The heroines of the films “History without censorship” are also more often sexualized than the heroes. Only among the main characters Emilia Plater and Elżbieta Łokietkówna escape this fate, and in the case of Marie Curie, sexual themes are clearly marked, although the film itself retains an epic style. This tendency to emphasize the sexual aspect of human nature more strongly when describing women compared to men is certainly more noticeable in “Historia bez cenzury” than in the other channels analysed here. Thus, the creators of historical channels notice the presence of women in history and do not ignore female themes. However, the way in which the heroines of historical events are presented is influenced by the specifics of the medium².

Based on this, the authors of this article decided to conduct a relevant study on women's themes on Ukrainian historical YouTube channels and then make a comparative analysis of this aspect on Ukrainian and Polish historical YouTube channels.

Therefore, **the purpose of the publication** is to clarify the place, role, and context of women based on the analysis of video materials from Ukrainian and Polish history from ancient times to the present day, posted on

² Ibidem, pp. 433-434.

leading Ukrainian and Polish historical YouTube channels. As well as to identify the top female figures who arouse the greatest interest from viewers.

The analysis of research and publications

Today we have a number of scientific works devoted to the gender issue, the place of women in the history of Ukraine and the world in general. These works are either exceptionally informative or, on the contrary, debatable. In most of them, the prevailing opinion is that the role of women, unlike men, is diminished in history. However, there are practically no scientific developments on the study of this aspect on influential social networks, among which YouTube³ occupies a dominant position, by applying special computer methods that have not been used in this way before.

It is worth noting that this method is only gaining momentum and is quite interesting⁴. Among such works, we can single out the already mentioned scientific article by W. Werner, N. Sypniewska, Z. Szymczak, M. Stachura, A. Stryjakowski, B. Staszak, A. Trzoss, and C. Kleist⁵, where the authors used a delete computer methods of EDA (distribution of data and central tendency) and Correspondence Analysis for data analysis.

L. Vovchuk⁶ also wrote about top female figures on Ukrainian historical YouTube channels. The author explored the place of Roksolana - a famous woman in the history of Ukraine, Turkey, and Poland.

³ W. Werner, L. Vovchuk, *Central Figures and Events of Ukrainian History in the Light of Content Analysis of Ukrainian Historical YouTube Channels from 2014 to 2022*, "Skhidnoievropeyskyi istorychnyi visnyk" ["East European Historical Bulletin"], no. 28, 2023, pp. 241-242.

⁴ A. Trzoss, W. Werner, C. Kleist, K. Kwiatkowska-Moskalewicz, M. Moskalewicz, *The politicisation of historical memory on Twitter: "Positive antisemitism" in the Holocaust debate in Poland*, "Rethinking History", 27(4), 2023, pp. 780–810; L. Vovchuk, W. Werner, *Between rebellion and loyalty: decisive moments of Ukrainian history of the 17th - early 18th centuries according to modern historical consciousness*, "Eminak", no. 2, 2024, pp. 44-61. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.33782/eminak2024.2\(46\).705](https://doi.org/10.33782/eminak2024.2(46).705).

⁵ Werner, Sypniewska, Szymczak, Stachura, Stryjakowski, Staszak, Trzoss, Kleist, *op.cit.*, pp. 409-435.

⁶ L. Vovchuk, "The Ukrainian woman who tamed the third world: the perception of Roksolana by Ukrainians on Ukrainian historical YouTube channels", in *The 5th International scientific and practical conference "European congress of scientific achievements" (May 20-22, 2024)*, Barca Academy Publishing, Barcelona, 2024, pp. 298-302.

The results of the research

The study was conducted in several stages. The empirical basis of the study was videos from the most popular Ukrainian historical YouTube channels. When selecting these historical YouTube channels, 2 criteria were taken: 1) the number of subscribers, which should not be less than 15 thousand, which indicates the interest and importance of the video content of this channel; 2) the presence of videos about women in the history of Ukraine and in the general history of the world. As a result, 13 Ukrainian historical YouTube channels were selected (fig. 1), which are quite popular among Ukrainian viewers of these channels. It is interesting that it is the Ukrainian historical YouTube channel of Iryna Farion that has the most videos about various famous Ukrainian women who left a bright mark on the history of the country with their activities⁷.

The next step in the research was to create a database based on watching videos on Ukrainian historical YouTube channels selected by the researchers. The number of viewed video material reached 100 units. These are videos that were made during 2016-2024. The films were annotated (using tags grouped into categories). The main categories of this database were:

1. the presence of a woman/women in the video. In order to ensure the accuracy of the data, the presence of a woman was assessed on a scale of their influence in the video: 4 – the main character (for example, a video about Anna of Kiev – the daughter and princess of Yaroslav the Wise and her role in the political life of France⁸); 3 – important, but not the main one, but playing an important role in a certain issue (for example, Hanna Zolotarenko - the third wife of Hetman Bohdan Khmelnytskyi, who issued universals in her own name, secretly managed the Hetman's treasury, and, with authority, managed the family affairs of the Khmelnytskyi family⁹); 2 repeated mention of

⁷ Iryna Farion, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/@IrynaFarion>.

⁸ *Taiemnytsi velykykh Ukraintsiv. Anna Kyivska* [Secrets of the great Ukrainians. Anna of Kyiv], 1+1, 2021, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kG4mLdcpqWM>.

⁹ *Taiemnytsi velykykh Ukraintsiv. Bohdan Khmelnytskyi* [Secrets of the great Ukrainians. Bohdan Khmelnytskyi], 1+1, 2021, URL: <https://cutt.ly/geVWsf0j>.

- various female characters and emphasis on their role in the main plot (for example, Maria Dobroneha – younger sister of Yaroslav the Wise, princess of Poland¹⁰); 1 – a passing mention of a female character (for example, Anastasia Fedorovna – mother of Bohdan Khmelnytskyi¹¹);
2. defining the role of a woman in the video (writer, actress, artist, mother, etc. For example, Lesya Ukrainka is a famous Ukrainian writer¹²);
 3. the topic of the video (political, military, economic, cultural, biographical)
 4. the place of the topic (history of Ukraine, universal history);
 5. historical period (antiquity, the Middle Ages, modern times, modern times, modern times);
 6. the number of views of the video.

The purpose of tagging was to conduct a quantitative study of the relationships between the specifics of women's portrayals in films and their other thematic properties.

The next stage was to conduct a machine learning study based on the Decision Tree (Classification and Regression Algorithm - CART) algorithm that can be used for both classification and regression tasks. It works by recursively partitioning the data into smaller and smaller subsets based on criteria of homogeneity (Gini's parameter) or information's gain (entropy). The goal is to create a tree structure that can accurately predict the target variable for new data points. This algorithm splits also the data into dependent and independent variables, where a relationship of dependency (for example, an effect-causation relationship) is assumed between the dependent variables and the independent variables. In our research, the dependent variable is the practice of portraying women as central characters in film. The set of independent variables are specific characteristics of the films and the female characters appearing in them (social role of the

¹⁰ *Taiemnytsi velykykh Ukraintsiv. Anna Kyivska* [Secrets of the great Ukrainians. Anna of Kyiv], 1+1, 2021, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kG4mLdcpqWM>.

¹¹ *Taiemnytsi velykykh Ukraintsiv. Bohdan Khmelnytskyi* [Secrets of the great Ukrainians. Bohdan Khmelnytskyi], 1+1, 2021, URL: <https://cutt.ly/geVWsf0j>.

¹² *Poetychne ta politychne zhyttia Lesi Ukrainky* [Lesya Ukrainka's poetic and political life], Iryna Farion, 2016, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ouUOwyF8rT0>.

character, popularity of the film, specific subject matter, and geographical location of the events).

The algorithm explores possible relationships between the dependent variable and the set of independent variables. The visualisation takes the form of a (inverted “crown” downwards) tree-like structure, in which movement to the left indicates a tendency to show women as the main characters and movement downwards (towards the “crown of the tree”) indicates an increase in the importance of the independent variables. In this particular case (fig. 2), the strongest correlation with the presentation of women as central figures in films was their role as art and cultural figures (philosophers and writers), the subject matter of the film (showing universal history) and the popularity of the film itself (high).

The producers of Ukrainian historical YouTube channels are most focused on producing videos about Ukrainian women or women who played an important role in Ukrainian history, rather than about women in general history (Fig. 3) however, women are more likely to play the lead role in films with general themes (Fig. 2). We were able to find this out by comparing the number of video views and the scale of female influence in the video. In the graph, the purple colour reflects women in Ukrainian history, and the orange colour shows women in general history.

Further research on this issue showed that the most popular videos among Ukrainian viewers of Ukrainian historical YouTube channels featuring women are videos on military, political, and cultural topics (Fig. 4). To identify this, the number of video views and video topics were analyzed. The popularity of military topics is explained, in our opinion, by the fact that these are videos that are directly dedicated to famous Ukrainian male figures who played an important role in the formation of Ukrainian statehood (for example, Bohdan Khmelnytskyi), which contain information about women who, although not the main characters of this video, play an important role in it.

As for political topics, in most videos, a woman plays the main or important role (for example, Princess Anna of Kiev, Inhiherda, Roksolana, etc.). These videos directly talk about the role of women in the history of Ukraine. The same can be said about cultural topics. These are videos that are

dedicated directly to highlighting the role of women in the formation of cultural trends in both the history of Ukraine and general history. For example, this is a video about Ukrainian writers Lesya Ukrainka¹³, Olha Kobylianska¹⁴, Daria Vikonska¹⁵, etc. Or a video about modern foreign actresses: Marilyn Monroe¹⁶.

Using the Correspondence Analysis method, we found that on the Ukrainian historical YouTube channels we selected, there are many videos where the main (Scale 4) or important (Scale 3) role of women is assigned to representatives of the New Time (Fig. 5). This is a period that covers the period from 1789 to 1914. This is, for example, a video about Marko Vovchok¹⁷ - a famous Ukrainian writer, translator. Her works had an anti-serfdom direction and described the historical past of Ukraine. In the 1860s, she gained considerable literary fame in Ukraine after the publication in 1857 of the Ukrainian-language collection "Folk Tales". She enriched Ukrainian literature with a number of new genres, in particular the social-feminist novel ("Institute"). The novel "Maroussia" in its French translation and adaptation became popular in Western Europe at the end of the 19th century. Olena Blavatska¹⁸ (1831-1891) was an outstanding philosopher, writer, and traveler. She was a highly educated woman, fluent in five foreign languages, deeply engaged in natural sciences, and painted beautifully.

¹³ *Poetychne ta politychne zhyttia Lesi Ukrainky [Lesya Ukrainka's poetic and political life]*, Iryna Farion, 2016, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ouUOwyF8rT0>.

¹⁴ *Olha Kobylianska — ukrainska feministka iz shliakhetnoi simi [Olha Kobylianska - Ukrainian feminist from a noble family]*, Iryna Farion, 2016, URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zGF-Dvv3_ke.

¹⁵ *Dariiia Vikonska – fenomenalne yavyshe ukrainskoi kultury [Daria Vikonska is a phenomenal phenomenon of Ukrainian culture]*, Iryna Farion, 2020, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yE5gGFhTTRI>.

¹⁶ *Zhinocha krasa. Ranishe bulo krashche? Naiharnishi zhinky v istorii svitu [Women's beauty. Was it better before? The most beautiful women in the history of the world]*, WAS, 2022, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HkY72QvKwdQ>.

¹⁷ *Marko Vovchok – Shevchenkova nakhennysia. Hostra, yak lezo, vpevnena, yak tyhryisia i samodostatnia, yak nebo [Marko Vovchok – Shevchenko's inspiration. Sharp as a blade, confident as a tigress, and self-sufficient as the sky]*, Iryna Farion, 2020, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5t73oCGSbka>.

¹⁸ *Medium Olena Blavatska – fenomen 19-ho stolittia [Medium Olena Blavatska - a phenomenon of the 19th century]*, *In search of truth*, 2022, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=puo2aAeExas>.

Further research results showed that videos about women in the role of “military” (Fig. 6) are of considerable interest among viewers of Ukrainian historical YouTube channels. And this is a video about Great women who changed the world, the beginning of which is tied to the Amazons. Amazons were warlike women who kept almost the entire world in fear. Legends go around the Amazon tribe: some believe in their existence, and some are convinced that this is another fairy-tale myth. Perhaps it is this aspect of the mystery surrounding the existence of the Amazons that attracts the attention of viewers the most.

In the same video, the next prominent women in the history of Ukraine and beyond are Princess Olga - a powerful, decisive and courageous ruler of Kyivan Rus, who made the trident the main symbol of the Ukrainian state. It also tells about the daughter of Yaroslav the Wise, Anna, the ruler of a third of the world, Roksolana.

In the second place there is “philosopher”. And here we are talking about Olena Blavatska, who is known to Ukrainians, Europe, the USA, and Latin America as the founder of the modern theosophical movement. She was among the founders of the Theosophical Society, the main goal of which was to promote the spread of the ancient teachings of Theosophy, or that Wisdom in the affairs of the Divine, which served as the spiritual basis for many great philosophical systems of the past, such as Neoplatonism, Gnosticism, and the ancient mystery schools¹⁹.

In the third place, there is a “dressmaker”. And this is about Jadwiga (Dunia) Husykovska, the first love of the famous Ukrainian writer of the 19th century Taras Shevchenko. This woman appears in the video about Taras Shevchenko²⁰ and is given considerable attention in the video. The fourth position belongs to the role of “aunt”, 5-6 - “doctor” and “queen”. If the 4th role includes exclusively women from Ukrainian history, then, in the case of the role of “queen”, we are talking about women from both Ukrainian and

¹⁹ B. Tsyrov, *Olena Petrivna Blavatska: korotkyi narys zhyttia i tvorchosti* [Olena Petrivna Blavatska: a brief outline of her life and work], *theosophy.in.ua*, URL: <https://theosophy.in.ua/pro-tt/zasnovniki-teosofskogo-tovaristva/o-p-blavatska>.

²⁰ *Yak Taras Shevchenko stav ukrainskym idolom?* [How did Taras Shevchenko become a Ukrainian idol?], *Real History*, 2023, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kxqh-0rnhRo>.

general history of the Middle Ages (Anna of Kyiv, Anastasia, Jadwiga of Anjou, Maria of Anjou, Elizabeth I.), Renaissance (Marie Antoinette) and New time (Victoria).

To find out the top female figure among the viewers of the Ukrainian historical YouTube channels we selected, we used two approaches: 1 - the number of views of videos with this person; 2 - by the number of videos with this person/role.

By the number of views of videos with a female figure (Fig 7), the top figure is Helena Blavatsky. The interest in this woman is explained by her mystery and mysticism. After all, in addition to the fact that she was a writer, publicist, founder of the Theosophical Society, and religious philosopher, Helena Blavatsky was a medium, occultist, and spiritualist. And it is this fact that attracts the most attention among viewers and the desire to understand it.

And by the number of videos with this person/role (Fig 8), the top ones are Roksolana, Anna Yaroslavivna, Ingigerda, 4-6 positions belong to Lesya Ukrainka, Helena (Motrona), Hanna Zolotarenko; 7-8 – Anna Smokina and Princess Olga.

Roksolana is undoubtedly one of the most famous women not only in Ukrainian and Turkish, but also in world history. Dozens of books and musical works have been written about her, she is depicted in many paintings (although they are all imaginary). The mistress of a third of the world - this is what Europeans once called Gürem Sultan or Roksolana. Roksolana fell into Tatar captivity and became a slave of the Turkish sultan. A woman who was able to capture the heart of the cruel Suleiman, become his wife and lay the foundations of a female sultanate.

The exact place of birth of Roksolana, as well as her Christian name, is unknown to science. In Suleiman's harem, she received the name Gürrem, for European diplomats of that time she remained a “native of Russia” (in various versions). In the Polish literary tradition, the name Alexandra is mentioned, in Ukrainian - Anastasia, Nastya. According to amateur historian Stanislav Zhevuskyi (referring to Samuel Tvardovskyi), she was the daughter of a priest from the Galician city of Rohatyn. In the famous historical novel

by Pavlo Zagrebelnyi “Roksolana” and Osyp Nazaruk “Roksolana”, the name of the main character is Nastya²¹.

Another prominent woman in Ukrainian history, who is of considerable interest among users of Ukrainian historical YouTube channels, is Anna of Kiev. She was the Queen of France, the daughter of Yaroslav the Wise, the granddaughter of Volodymyr the Great, and the niece of the Ukrainian saints Boris and Hlib. Anna Yaroslavna was a Ukrainian princess from Kiev, the most developed capital of Europe in the 11th century. Anna is one of the most prominent women of the Middle Ages, who glorified Ukraine throughout Europe. The first officially recorded emigrant from Ukraine to Europe. She was the only woman who corresponded with Pope Nicholas II.

In 1051, Anna of Kiev married the French monarch Henry I and became Queen of France. The Kiev princess brought to the French capital the Old Russian Gospel, written in Cyrillic and Glagolitic. Later, the Gospel was transferred to the Reims Cathedral, calling it the Reims Cathedral. It was there that all the kings of France until the 18th century, upon ascending the throne, swore an oath of allegiance to France during their coronation. Today, this invaluable document from the early Middle Ages is kept in the National Library in Paris²².

The third place in the hierarchical list by types/roles in the videos we analysed is given to Inhiherda, who was the mother of Anna of Kiev. Inhiherda was the daughter of King Olof III of Sweden and Astrid of Mecklenburg. She is also known by the Christian name Irina. Inhiherda was the second wife of Yaroslav the Wise.

Inhiherda is described in sources as a noble princess with a strong-willed disposition. Some researchers, talking about Inhiherda's strong-willed character, emphasize that this is due to her Scandinavian roots. However,

²¹ *Roksolana. Ukrainka, yaka pryborkala tretynu svitu [Roksolana. The Ukrainian woman who tamed a third of the world], In search of truth, 2023, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fcIJ9i3uBE>.*

²² *Ukraina. Povernennia svoiei istorii. Chastyna 1 [Ukraine. Reclaiming your story. Part 1], 1+1, 2016, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=j3LhEdsdAo8>.*

little attention is paid to the fact that the Swedish princess's lineage has a very significant Slavic component²³.

Lesya Ukrainka (real name Larisa Kosach) is a prominent Ukrainian writer of the 19th century. It is interesting that Lesya Ukrainka came from a family of women known in Ukrainian history. Her mother, Olena Pchilka, was a famous writer, her aunt Olena Kosach was also a writer²⁴. In the video about Lesya Ukrainka, who acts as the main character there, these women are mentioned, but there they occupy important, but not main roles.

A rather interesting personality is Helena Chaplinska or Motrona Khmelnytska. Today, the biography of Motrona Chaplinska remains an open question, since it is unknown when and where she was born, who her parents were, and why she moved to the territory of Chyhyryn. However, it is assumed that she came from a family of Polish nobility. In addition, it is worth noting that the name Elena is used by historians for metaphorical purposes, due to the fact that the Polish scholars began to compare Motrona with Elena the Beautiful. However, this comparison pointed not so much to Chaplinska's beauty as to the tragic female fate.

On December 28, 1648, Hetman Khmelnytskyi married Helena after returning from Zamost. Patriarch Paisius of Jerusalem gave him his blessing for this marriage. Ambassadors from Moscow, Semihrod, the Sultan, Moldavia, and Wallachia arrived in Kyiv for this significant event. Helena became Khmelnytskyi's second wife.

Although Bohdan Khmelnytskyi himself passionately loved Helena, his entourage (primarily his sons) wanted to get rid of her. Among the elders, Helena was called “Lyashka” and was suspected of having relations with her ex-husband Danylo Chaplynskyi. In May 1651, Matrona's nephew, Tymish Khmelnytskyi, known for his fierce temper, executed his hated stepmother while his father was on a campaign, hanging her at the gates of the estate. This was reported by the nobleman Kszytsky on June 14, 1651: “They say that Khmelnytskyi ordered his wife to be hanged because D. Chaplynskyi's

²³ *Inhiherda, pryntsesa shvedska, Velyka kniahynia Kyivska [Inhiherda, Princess of Sweden, Grand Duchess of Kiev], Ukrainika, 2021, UKR: <https://www.libr.dp.ua/?do=ukrainica&lng=1&id=5&idg=99>.*

²⁴ *Lesia Ukrainka: istoriia zhyttia, kariera i literatura [Lesia Ukrainka: life story, career and literature], tochkazboru, 2023, URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KwneraZj6ls>.*

intercepted letters to her were discovered, asking her to bury all the treasures in the ground and poison Khmelnytsky himself²⁵.

The seventh position is occupied by Anna Smokina, who was the first wife of Bohdan Khmelnytskyi. Around 1623, Bohdan Khmelnytskyi, already a mature man and an experienced warrior, brought his young wife Hanna or Anna to the farm. No documentary evidence of the bride's family origin has been preserved. The first wife was calm, balanced and did not interfere in her husband's affairs. All of Bohdan Khmelnytskyi's children were from his marriage to Hanna. The exact number of descendants is also unknown to us. We are talking about the sons of Tymosh, the future hetman Yurii and, possibly, Hryhoriyi, who probably died as an infant, as well as six or eight daughters. The names of three are known: Stefanida, Olena, Kateryna²⁶.

So, as we can see, the top position of the female figure on Ukrainian historical YouTube channels is somewhat different. By the number of video views, the top woman is Helena Blavatsky, the interest in whom is explained by her mystery and mysticism. At the same time, by the number of videos with a female person/role, the dominant positions are occupied by Roksolana, Anna of Kyiv, Inhiherda. Thus, only from the YouTube channels we selected, videos about Roksolana were shot: 1+1 (viewed by 1,249,207 people) and named after T.H. Shevchenko (viewed by 734,319 people). Women such as Helena Chaplynska, Hanna Zolotarenko, Anna Smokina are interesting figures through the prism of the male figure of Bohdan Khmelnytskyi. These three women were his wives and each of them played a decisive role not only in Khmelnytskyi's life, but also in the history of Ukraine.

²⁵ O. Pyskun, *Helena Chaplynska: mify ta realnist* [*Helena Chaplynska: myths and reality*], *Kraieznavcho-etnografichni narysy*, N. d., URL: <http://dspace.nbu.gov.ua/bitstream/handle/123456789/17599/15-Piskun.pdf?sequence=1>.

²⁶ S. Sehed, *Try druzhyny Bohdana Khmelnytskoho Lokalna istoriia* [*The Three Wives of Bohdan Khmelnytskyi*], 2023, URL: <https://localhistory.org.ua/texts/statti/tri-druzhini-getmana/>.

**Fig. 1. Table of the most popular ukrainian historical Youtube channels
(data collected on 11/30/2024)**

№	Channel name	Number of channel subscribers
1	TV channel 1+1	3,3 million
2	named after T.H. Shevchenko	821 thousand
3	History without myths	645 thousand
4	WAS: Popular History	271 thousand
5	Iryna Faron	331 thousand
6	History for adults	212 thousand
7	tochkazboru	118 thousand
8	In search of truth	78,6 thousand
9	Real History	47,6 thousand
10	The last hetman	27,8 thousand
11	Oleksandr Alfiorov	27,5 thousand
12	biographer_ua	153 thousand
13	express_ua	20,1 thousand

Fig. 2. Decision tree visualization

Fig. 3. The place of women's theme in history

Fig. 4. The theme of the film where the figure of a woman appears the most

Fig. 5. Top historical period

Fig. 6. The hierarchy of women is compiled by the number of views of videos with this person

Fig. 7. The hierarchy of women is compiled by the number of views of videos with this person

Fig. 8. The hierarchy of women is compiled by the number of videos with this person/role

Conclusion

Today, the creators of Ukrainian and Polish historical YouTube channels notice the presence of women in history and do not ignore women's topics. The topic of women is also present in videos about men. Only there the woman does not have the main role, but is important or simply mentioned in the role of mother, wife, sister, friend of the male protagonist. Among Ukrainian historical YouTube channels, the largest number of videos about famous Ukrainian women (more than 20), including princesses, writers, artists, actresses, liaisons, is on Iryna Farion's YouTube channel. The women she talks about are described in great detail, but from a clearly defined perspective subordinated to patriotic education.

In most cases, creators of videos about women on Ukrainian historical YouTube channels provide not only information about their origin, place of birth, family, status, preferences, but also try to tell about various sometimes piquant, mysterious aspects of their lives. This is explained by the producers' desire to attract the attention of viewers. After all, this is a well-known method in psychology. People are interested in all kinds of legends, mysterious stories, and so on. What is difficult to confirm, to prove. It is worth noting that the attention of video producers on Ukrainian historical YouTube channels is more focused on producing videos about women in the history of Ukraine, rather than about women in general history. This phenomenon is explained by the issue of the revival of historical memory and historical consciousness, which are the basis of the country's development. Top female figures are Roksolana, Anna of Kyiv, Inhiherda, Helena Blavatska, the three wives of Bohdan Khmelnytskyi.

Our research, both quantitative (correspondence analysis, statistical analysis) and qualitative (plot model analysis), shows that YouTube as a Web 2.0 tool has created new and attractive communication models and the functioning of historical narratives, breaking the patterns of traditional literature and even constituting an alternative.

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